

Thioketonic Esters. Part I. Synthesis of Ethyl Thioacetoacetate and its Derivatives.

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The present investigation was taken up with a view to observe more rigidly the existing similarity between C:S and C:O groups. It was also thought necessary to observe whether the CS-group can impart any negative character to the adjacent CH₂-group like the carbonyl group in diketones and ketonic esters.

The present paper describes the preparation and properties of ethyl thioacetoacetate* Me·CS·CH₂·CO₂Et which has been synthesised thus :

The mercaptan which is thus formed in the course of the reaction, evidently tautomerises to the keto-form which is supported by subsequent estimation of keto-enol by Meyer's method of bromination. The substance was subjected to ketonic hydrolysis with a view to obtain thioacetone (Me)₂CS. The compound does not react with sodium carbonate or bicarbonate. On boiling with dilute sulphuric acid it

* A compound named as "ethyl thioacetoacetate" was first prepared by Buchka (*Ber.*, 1885, 18, 2090) and later on by Michaelis, Phillips and Delisle (*Ber.*, 1890, 23, 559; 1887, 20, 2038) and Schonbrodt (*Annalen.*, 1889 253 168) by the action of sulphur dichloride on monosodi-derivative of ethyl acetoacetate. But a wrong nomenclature has really been applied to the compound, as it is a true sulphide and the constitutional formula is

which afterwards was confirmed by Buchka and Sprague (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2541).

evolves carbon dioxide profusely like ethyl acetoacetate along with some sulphuretted hydrogen proving that it contains an esterified carboxyl group. On completion of hydrolysis no oil was found to be left behind. Evidently if ethyl thioacetoacetate had got the constitution $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2\text{Et}$ then on subjecting it to ketone hydrolysis it should have yielded thioacetone along with carbon dioxide. But if thioacetone had actually been formed, it evidently suffered decomposition in the course of the reaction, which is in accordance with Baumann and Fromm (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 2592) who during the preparation of trithioacetone suspected the formation of thioacetone as a readily decomposing volatile oil. In the end of the process the presence of acetone in the solution was ascertained. It, therefore, follows that thioacetone actually resulted in the course of hydrolysis according to the equation, $\text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CO}_2\text{Et} = \text{CH}_3 \cdot \text{CS} \cdot \text{CH}_3 + \text{CO}_2 + \text{EtOH}$, and the thioacetone was decomposed by water into acetone and sulphuretted hydrogen. Similar results were obtained when it was boiled with dilute caustic potash.

It was also noticed that the same ester always results by the action of potassium hydrosulphide on the *cis*- or *trans*-chlorocrotonic ester, and hence it was unnecessary to separate the isomers. The ethyl thioacetoacetate thus prepared was found to behave as a true ketone. With phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine and aniline it evolves copiously sulphuretted hydrogen even in the cold. On treating the ester with phenylhydrazine in the cold and completing the reaction on a water-bath, Knorr's phenylmethylpyrazolone (I) was obtained quantitatively along with a quantity of its dehydro-product (II).

The reaction on being performed with a little excess of phenylhydrazine, nearly 50% of the ester was converted into the dehydro-product (II). The ester on being treated with *p*-nitrophenylhydrazine,

and phenylhydrazine-*p*-sulphonic acid yielded the corresponding pyrazolones.

The ester was found to react with metallic sodium with brisk evolution of hydrogen in ethereal suspension like ethyl acetoacetate and the sodium derivative was thrown down as a white powder. This is so very hygroscopic that it was found to be extremely difficult to analyse. Further investigations of the compound and analogous compounds are in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Ethyl Thioacetoacetate.—Ethyl chlorocrotonate (100 g.) was treated with potassium hydrosulphide (48 g.) at 0°. The reaction ensued instantaneously and potassium chloride began to separate. The reaction was then completed on a water-bath under reflux for two hours. The whole of the mixture was then diluted with water when the major portion of the oil settled at the bottom and then after acidifying the supernatant liquid, the oil was extracted by means of ether. The ethereal extract after drying over anhydrous sodium sulphate was freed from ether and subjected to vacuum distillation. The fraction coming between 60° and 110° at 15 mm. was refractionated and the portion boiling at 75°/15 mm. was found to be pure ethyl thioacetoacetate (yield 30%): $d_{31}^{\circ} = 1.0554$ and $n_{26}^{\circ} = 1.4712$. (Found: C, 50.06; H, 7.02; S, 21.3; M.W., 144. $C_6H_{10}O_2S$ requires C, 48.3; H, 6.9; S, 21.9 per cent.; M.W., 147).

Ethyl thioacetoacetate is an orange, mobile liquid possessing sweet ester-like smell. It can decolourise an alcoholic solution of iodine proving the existence of the SH-group. It evolves sulphuretted hydrogen in contact with phenylhydrazine, hydroxylamine, toluidine, etc. in the cold. On boiling with 10% sulphuric acid it is completely transformed into acetone, sulphuretted hydrogen and carbon dioxide in 4 hours. Similarly with 10% caustic potash or soda, alkali sulphides and acetone are produced. On boiling with the theoretical amount of alcoholic caustic potash, a white precipitate is obtained. The amount of potassium in the compound indicated that it was a mixture of potassium salts of thioacetoacetic and acetoacetic acids. Evidently it points out that in the course of hydrolysis the ketonic sulphur had partially been replaced by oxygen, and the presence of potassium sulphide was proved in the

alcoholic extract. In the presence of metallic sodium in ethereal suspension it vigorously evolved hydrogen and formed the sodium derivative as a white powder. The sodium derivative was found to be very hygroscopic. The ester on being added to an alcoholic solution of sodium ethoxide in molecular proportions gave no precipitate, which evidently led to the conclusion that the monosodio-derivative is soluble in alcohol.

Phenylmethylpyrazolone.—Ethyl thioacetate (5 g.) was treated with phenylhydrazine (3.5 g.) in the cold, and allowed to remain for 4-5 minutes when the vigorous evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen ceased. The reaction was completed by heating on a water-bath for 4 hours. It was then washed with ether to remove the resinous matter and then digested with warm alcohol, when the pyrazolone (m.p. 127°) dissolved leaving behind the less soluble dehydro-product (yield 60% of pyrazolone and 20% of the dehydro-product). (Found: N, 16.28. $C_{10}H_{10}ON_2$ requires N, 16.09 per cent.).

Dehydrophenylmethylpyrazolone.—The ester (5 g.) was heated with double the amount of phenylhydrazine on a water-bath for 6 hours. The resulting product was washed with ether, and then with alcohol. The residue was crystallised from acetic acid. It began to char at 246° and finally decomposed completely at 320° (yield 50%). (Found: N, 16.97. $C_{20}H_{18}ON_4$ requires N, 16.96 per cent.).

Phenylmethylpyrazolone-p-sulphonic Acid.—The ester (3 g.) and phenylhydrazine-p-sulphonic acid (4 g.) were heated on a water-bath for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was then digested with hot water and the first and the second crop of crystals that separated were collected and found to melt with decomposition at 320° (yield 70%). (Found: N, 11.02. $C_{10}H_{10}N_2O_4S$ requires N, 11.02 per cent.).

p-Nitrophenylmethylpyrazolone was similarly obtained. The reaction product was washed with petroleum ether and finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 218° (yield 40%). (Found: N, 19.32. $C_{10}H_9O_3N_3$ requires N, 19.18 per cent.).

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